

Société Française pour l'Étude des Toxines
French Society of Toxinology

29^{èmes} Rencontres en Toxinologie
29th Meeting on Toxinology

30 novembre - 01 décembre 2023
November 30 - December 01, 2023
Institut Pasteur, Paris

Toxines: De la nature au labo

Toxins: From the wild to the lab

avec le concours de – supported by:

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Session "Toxin functional exploration"
Selected Speaker

Building up a pipeline for assessing potential molecular targets of conotoxins with unknown mode of action

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Venomics studies on cone snails have unveiled a vast diversity of peptide neurotoxin structures present in their venom, named "conotoxins". Conotoxins are the major constituents of the venom and target neural and neuromuscular receptors allowing the cone snail to paralyse or stun the prey. During the last two decades, the advances in transcriptomic techniques have let the discovery of more than 25,000 conotoxins. However, transcriptomic analysis does not permit to isolate the conotoxins and determine their molecular target and mode of action through bioassays. As a consequence, the number of conotoxins with a known mode of action is significantly lower: to date (September 2023) 999 conotoxins are registered in UNIPROT with a known molecular target. On the other hand, the use of AI advances in the study of the structure of proteins has come up with the development of powerful tools to model *in silico* their 3D structure. Among them, AlphaFold has revealed itself as a good approach to model protein structures. The comparison between the modelled structures and the experimental ones shows that the AlphaFold-predicted and the experimentally-solved structures contained in UNIPROT are alike in most of the cases. The bioactivity of conotoxins, and of any other peptidic signals, depends on their 3D structure that determines the assembly between the toxin and the target, but also on the sequence, on which it depends the chemical interactions within the pocket. In this approach, we will focus on the first factor: the 3D structure. We have built a database with more than 25,000 published conotoxin sequences. By using AlphaFold, we will model their 3D structures in order to build another database containing their theoretical structures. Through the use of the recently disclosed bioinformatic tools RUPEE and Foldseek, we will compare the 3D structure of the published conotoxins with an unknown target with the structures of those with a known target obtained from UNIPROT. For those with an acceptable match, it is proposed that both conotoxins will likely have the same molecular target/mode of action. Even though the results will be biased by the number and types of known modes of action, data-mining will allow us to categorize conotoxins and lead future bioassay studies, allowing to optimize time and lab resources. Also, the result of those bioassays will help to test the model.

Keywords: AlphaFold, cone snail, conotoxin, Foldseek, mode of action, RUPEE, venomics.

Jeudi 30 novembre / Thursday, November 30

9h00 – 9h10: Welcome to the RT29 – Sylvie DIOCHOT (SFET President)

9h10 – 12h10

Session 1 | Venom Research

Chairpersons: Loïc QUINTON & Michel RONJAT

9h10 – 9h40: Michel M. DUGON (Univ. of Galway, The Ryan Institute, Galway, Ireland)
Venom potency and composition of European spiders

9h40 – 10h10: Axel TOUCHARD (Cornell Univ., Ithaca, NY, USA)
Exploring the diversity of ants to discover novel neurotoxic venom peptides

10h10 – 10h40: Aude VIOLETTE, Rudy FOURMY (Alphabiotoxine Laboratory, Montroeuil-au-Bois, Belgium)
How Alphabiotoxin brings the wild to your lab

10h40 – 11h10: Coffee Break / Posters & Sponsors

11h10 – 11h30: Julien SLAGBOOM (Amsterdam Institute of Molecular and Life Sciences, Vrije Univ. Amsterdam, The Netherlands)
Acetylcholine binding protein affinity profiling of neurotoxins in snake venoms with parallel toxin identification by high throughput venomics

11h30 – 11h50: Mátyás A. BITTENBINDER (Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, The Netherlands)
Bloody insights: using organ-on-chip technology to study haemorrhagic activities of snake venoms on endothelial tubules

11h50 – 12h10: Zahrmina RATIBOU (CRIOBE, Univ. de Perpignan, Perpignan, France)
*Characterization of the venom of *Conus canonicus* from Mayotte island*

12h10 – 12h20: Artem KONDRATSKYI – Nanion Technologies

12h20 – 12h50: 2-min highlights of 15 selected posters

12h50 – 13h00: Group photo

13h00 – 14h50: Lunch / Posters & Sponsors

14h50 – 17h20

Session 2 | Toxin functional exploration

Chairpersons: Christian LEGROS & Sébastien DUTERTRE

14h50 – 15h20: Emmanuel LEMICHEZ (Bacterial Toxins, Institut Pasteur, Paris, France)
New partner in the perception of the mechanical properties of the environment by cell anchoring receptors influences infection by ExPEC producing CNF1 toxin

15h20 – 15h50: Annette NICKE (Walther Straub Institute of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Ludwig-Maximilians-Univ. of Muenchen, Muenchen, Germany)
Characterization of α -conotoxins and their structure activity relationships by two-electrode voltage clamp analysis

15h50 – 16h20: Steve PEIGNEUR (Toxicology and Pharmacology, Univ. of Leuven, Leuven, Belgium)
The sobering sting: a novel cone snail venom-derived antagonist of cannabinoid receptors

16h20 – 16h40: Juan Carlos García GALINDO (Dept. de Química Orgánica-INBIO, Univ. de Cádiz, Puerto Real, Spain)
Building up a pipeline for assessing potential molecular targets of conotoxins with unknown mode of action